

How To Send A Fax From Gmail For Free

Forget about using a fax machine ever again. Nowadays you can send a fax from Gmail without needing a fax machine or a fax line. In this tutorial you'll learn how to send your first fax using this method.

Fax-to-email services let you send fax from Gmail in just a few steps, by providing you with a virtual fax line that is ready to be used in minutes. We recommend you create a free account with a service like RingCentral Fax which are fully compatible with Gmail addresses.

Sending a Fax from Gmail

1. Create a new email message by clicking on the Compose button.
2. Enter the recipient's fax number on the TO field of the email message. Then, add @ and the domain of your fax service next to it. It should look like this: faxnumber@faxservice.com For instance, if you need to send fax to the number 1-343-777-5555 using eFax, this is what you would need to type on the TO field:
13437775555@efaxsend.com.
3. If you need to add a cover page, use the Subject field and/or the message's body. You don't need to include a cover page if you don't want to. It's an optional step for people that need to include additional information about the fax transmission. The design of your cover pages can be changed through your online fax account at any time.
4. Add the files that are going to be converted to fax. Online fax services work with dozens of different formats including popular ones such as PDF, DOC, XLS, JPG, TIFF and TXT. To attach the file(s), click on the paperclip icon (Attach files) on the bottom of the composing window. Mobile app users will find this icon on the top-right corner of the screen.

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5. Make sure all the information is correct before you send a fax online. Click on Send and your document will be sent for conversion, then forwarded to the receiver's fax machine.

It shouldn't take more than a couple of minutes to complete the transmission. You'll get a confirmation message on your Gmail account with all the details of your fax. If there's an error along the way, fax services will re-try sending it multiple times to ensure your fax reaches its destination.

The first difference between a "traditional" email and a Gmail fax is that you enter the number on the TO field, followed by @ and the domain of your online fax provider.

The second difference when you send fax from Gmail is that the fax contents have to be attached to the email message. This file will be automatically converted into a fax document, and remain fully compatible with common fax machines.

Best Gmail Fax Services of 2020

An online fax service will give you a Gmail fax number, enabling you to send and receive faxes without leaving the email interface. It will also give you a domain that you have to add to the recipient's number when composing an email to fax (more about in the step-by-step guide below), and provide additional features such as mobile apps and integration with Google Docs.

You can send fax online free by signing up for a free trial with any of these recommended services:

RingCentral [hippa complain electronic fax service](#) Fax. This company has a fax from email solution as a stand-alone product or as part of their virtual office suite, RingCentral Office. With years in the market, this company is always including new features to online fax. They provide coverage in the US, Canada and UK.

Sending fax with Gmail doesn't have to be hard. Online fax is the perfect solution for small businesses that want to decrease the time and money they spend with traditional fax machines. Fax to email technology is easy to integrate in your company. Even if you currently have a dedicated fax line in place, you can transfer it to a digital one and keep using your existing number.

To send fax online you just need your computer and an online fax service. The steps to compose a fax are so simple that even people who consider themselves to be technically challenged won't have a problem with the process. On the other hand, you can create a Gmail account at anytime for free.

The availability of free alternatives makes it very easy to find a service that works for you. Besides price, there are other factors worth keeping into account, such as support, speed, compatible apps, file compatibility and the type of free Google fax numbers they provide.